

Nexus between the Brazilian climate commitment on deforestation and agricultural resources: a view of the CLEWs approach

- Lucas Silva Carvalho, COPPE/UFRJ, Brazil
- 13/02/2025

- **Keywords:** deforestation, land cover change, land uses change, crop production, nexus, sustainable transitions, CLEWs; OSeMOSYS.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Kane Alexander, Taco Niet and Osmar Cuadra for the training and attention, to my class colleagues for valuable insights exchanges, the EMP-LAC crew, and in particular Rudolf Yeganyan for the excellent work in organizing the EMP-LAC program. I also thank the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG), the World Bank Group, and the 2050 Pathways Platform for providing the platform for this important capacity building initiative to take place.

This report was created during the EMP-LAC 25 capacity building event organized by the Climate Compatible Growth Programme, International Centre for Theoretical Physics, World Bank Group, 2050 Pathways Platform, Universidad de la Matanza and the British Embassy of Buenos Aires.

I would like to thanks WBG, 2050 Pathways Platform by funding.

This material has been produced with support from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme. CCG is funded by UK aid from the UK government. However, the views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.
”

Executive Summary

Brazil faces the challenge of expanding its agricultural production without threatening forests, and it must also deal with the potential impacts of climate change on agriculture. In this sense, this work aims to understand the relationships between deforestation control and agricultural production by verifying the impact of deforestation control on land use and technological change in agricultural water technologies. Trend scenarios and deforestation control policies were developed, as well as scenarios considering the impact of decreased agricultural productivity. It was observed that deforestation control leads to changes in area and type of agricultural technologies related to water use; the impacts of climate change, such as reduced rainfall and consequently decreased agricultural productivity, lead to a significant expansion of irrigated systems. Policies are needed that plan the use of land in the country and natural resources jointly, to be able to better deal with the relationships that exist between different sectors. It is necessary to build policies that encompass economic incentives for transitions to more productive and sustainable systems.

1. Introduction

Brazil's main source of greenhouse gas emissions comes from the AFOLU sector, which includes deforestation. As an agricultural exporter, Brazil is expected to expand its agricultural production to meet various SDGs (such as hunger and energy), both nationally and globally. Globally, agriculture is one of the main drivers of ecosystem conversion (such as forests) (IPBES, 2019) and the economic activity that consumes the most water. Increasing production without compromising environmental resources in a world of climate change is an urgent challenge.

The harms of deforestation are diverse. Without its control, it is not possible to meet the country's commitments under the Paris Agreement (Rochedo et al., 2018). Additionally, it is reported that besides the impacts of global climate changes, such as on the hydrological regime, deforestation can accentuate these impacts on a regional scale, impacting agricultural production. Most Brazilian agriculture is rainfed (about 90%), with only 10% being irrigated (ANA, 2017), making it more vulnerable to climate changes.

In this sense, this work aims to understand the relationships between deforestation control and agricultural production. The objectives of the work are:

- To elucidate the consequences of deforestation control on land use and technological change in agriculture;
- To verify the likely impact of reduced crop productivity, due to climate change on rainfall patterns, on natural resources.

2. Methodology

In the current exercise, the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) tool was used. It has been improved and finds applications for various climate policies related in developing countries in Latin America and the Caribbean (Plazas-Nino et al., 2023).

The model data feed was done through several databases. They were: (i) The Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit; regarding energy data; (ii) The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), for agriculture and water resources data; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), for land cover data; International Energy Agency (IEA) for energy data.

The time horizon was from 2020 to 2050. The projected annual demand growth for crops and biofuel was associated with population growth, which in Brazil is low (0.43%). The growth of the built-up area considered between 2020 and 2050 was 27%, following observations from the previous period (OECD, 2025). The demand for water resources was based on the growth of the country's real gross domestic product, assumed to be 1.22% (Statista, 2025).

The model was populated with data, and a simplified representation of the energy, land use, and water systems for Brazil, the reference energy system, was built following Cannone and Allington (2021). The main crops of the country were listed, which are soy, maize and wheat as crop production, and sugarcane as a biofuel-dedicated crop.

Considering the country’s context and the objectives of the modelling exercise, four scenarios were constructed (Table 1):

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Base line	Reference Permitted Deforestation (no policies) No climate change impacts on agriculture	-Weakness governance -Climate optimism (no impacts of climate change)
Zero_def	-Controlling deforestation -No climate change impacts on agriculture	NDC Commitment – zero deforestation from 2030
Base_imp_CC	Permitted deforestation Climate change impacts in agriculture	Nothing is done. Inaction. Deforestation free and probable climate change impacts on agriculture (less 15% yield all crops)
Zero_def_CC	- Controlling deforestation - Climate change impacts on agriculture	Zero deforestation from 2030 Climate change impacts on agriculture (less 15% yield all crops)

Table 1. Scenarios

In the real world, the Brazilian government committed to making “continuous efforts to achieve zero deforestation, by eliminating illegal deforestation and compensating for the legal suppression of native vegetation” by 2030 (MMA, 2024). In other words, there is talk of net zero deforestation. This measure was interpreted/introduced with the release of the model to deforest until 2030 and thereafter it is no longer possible to convert forests to other uses.

Given the rationality of the model and the circumstances of the modelling exercise, it is appropriate to signal that the land use cover generated in the base scenario is distinct from the original. This is because the model allocates lands to forests due to its negative cost, and because not all coverages had their accurate representation, such as the crop sector itself. In this sense, a deforestation control exercise is based on the forest area offered by the base scenario. It is on this area that the deforestation restriction is made from 2030 onwards.

Regarding the impact of climate change on agriculture, the alteration in the rainfall regime was considered, such as the increased occurrence of drought periods. This was translated in the model by assuming a 15% loss of crop productivity and cultivation forms (Costa et al., 2017).

3. Results

In terms of area, the land use change presents numbers that may seem small, especially in terms of the percentage of area compared to the territory analyzed, which. We must interpret the data correctly considering the due scale.

The focus of this study was to analyze the consequences of land use changes. The results presented different behaviors for the scenarios regarding land use. For the initial years, they show the same trend, where deforestation is allowed, but soon after, the restriction on deforestation from 2030 leads to significant changes in trend and values in the studied resources.

The base scenario presents a conversion of forest lands in the order of 66.10^3 km^2 . The base_imp_CC scenario presents a greater conversion, in the value of 157.10^3 km^2 , fig.1

Fig.1. land use change

Another interesting result is to observe what happens with the yield. In the zerodef scenario, a growth in the yield of two crops (maize and wheat) is observed. This growth is linked to the adoption of irrigation technology (fig. 2)

zero_def

Delta zero_def-base

Fig. 2. Crop yields

Regarding land use by crops and their respective technologies, the scenarios that adopt deforestation control present a change in the trend of the base scenario. In the base scenario, irrigated crops are reduced, reaching zero from 2035 onwards. In the zero deforestation scenarios, they also reduce while deforestation is allowed (initial years), but then there is a reversal of trend, where the use of irrigated crop technology increases considerably. In the zero_def scenarios, we have a use of $78. 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ in 2050 and in the zero_def_CC scenario there are figures of $188. 10^3 \text{ km}^2$ (fig. 3)

Area By Crop (Irrigated)
proj_base

zerodef

zerodef_CC

Fig.3. area by crop (irrigated)

Water consumption follows the pattern of land resource. In the base scenario, the use of irrigation technology decreases and consequently water consumption. In the zero_def scenario, it starts with the same numbers and downward trend, but from the adoption of the deforestation restriction, the use of irrigated area and water consumption grows, reaching about 51 billions m^3 of water. However, when zero deforestation and the impact of climate change on productivity are considered, a lower value of 80 billion m^3 of water is presented, reaching 2050 with 122 billions m^3 , which represents more than double the zero_def scenario (which does not consider climate change).(fig. 4)

Fig.4 water consumption

5. Discussion

While the energy system seems aligned with Brazil's contribution to a world below 2 degrees, the land use part continued to show forest conversion in the base scenario. This fact, as a trend, is a challenge for the country. But here, the interest is not the impact of deforestation, but the impact of deforestation control.

The conversion of forest lands to agriculture is part of the model's rationality. When we put an increase in the demand for agricultural products, without area restrictions, an increase in agricultural area and a decrease in forest area were expected. When considering lower crop productivity, a larger area is observed to meet this demand, as was possible to observe in the base_impac_CC scenario.

On the other hand, when we put an increase in the demand for agricultural products with a growth restriction in area (zero def scenarios), the model has to resort to increasing productivity. In the present exercise, the way to produce more in the same unit of land area is through the adoption of irrigation technology. Under this context, the model migrates from technology, reduces its area of rainfed cultivation, and expands its area of irrigated crops, in general.

Due to the new configuration of land use, there are consequences in resources and technologies, revealing the nexus between different topics and sectors. It is possible to verify that to meet increasing demands, whether they are for food or biofuels, transformations in agriculture are necessary. To produce more without compromising forests, transitions to more productive models are needed, however, it is important to stress that these should be efficient in the use of resources, such as land and water. Otherwise, we will be replacing the problem of deforestation with conflicts over other resources (i.e. water).

In case the increase in productivity is centered on irrigation, there will be impacts on water consumption and also on energy in agriculture (machinery). It is also noted a greater vulnerability of the productive system because it is dependent on a variable (water) that can

also present scarcity and competition for other uses, which points to the need for the use and deepening of the CLEWs approach.

It is important to recognize some limitations of the model and the exercise. One of them is the conversion of forests to agriculture only, as other non-forest natural formations are also converted to agriculture in the real world. It is also noted that the impact of climate change on productivity varies according to the agricultural crop and region and may even increase. In the present study, only the reduction was considered and treated without distinction. Another aspect concerns the cost of technologies. Considering that the cost values of rainfed and irrigated cultivation modes are illustrative, it is not interesting to explore this variable. In this sense, we sought to explore the possibilities and resources of the model to perform comparative analyses with its limitations and resources.

7. Conclusion

Due to the new configuration of land use, there are consequences in resources and technologies, and the model has functionality for such analysis. Given the above, it is possible to verify how deforestation dynamics relate to the agricultural sector. The main one is with technological transformations necessary to meet demands, which is the migration to more productive technologies (in this case, irrigated crops). This leads to an increase in water and energy consumption. When the impacts of climate change, such as reduced rainfall and, consequently, agricultural productivity, lead to greater increment and dependence on irrigated systems.

It is necessary for policies that plan the use of land in the country and natural resources jointly. It is not opportune to cut down forests, for reasons of environmental and economic benefits. This adds to the need for regulation of the use of water resources and the construction of policies that encompass economic incentives for transitions to more productive and sustainable systems.

References

1. Agência Nacional de Águas (Brasil). Atlas irrigação: uso da água na agricultura irrigada / Agência Nacional de Águas. -- Brasília: ANA, 2017.
- 2 Allington, L., Cannone, C., Pappis, I., Barron, K. C., Usher, W., Pye, S., ... & To, L. S. (2022). Selected 'Starter kit' energy system modelling data for selected countries in Africa, East Asia, and South America (# CCG, 2021). Data in Brief, 42, 108021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.108021> (Accessed: 31 January 2024).
- 3 Costa L, Sant'Anna A A and Young C E F 2023 Barren lives: drought shocks and agricultural vulnerability in the Brazilian Semi-Arid Environ. Dev. Econ. 28 603–23
4. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (n.d.). FAOSTAT - Greenhouse Gas Emissions [Online]. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/GCE>
5. IPBES (2019): Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. E. S. Brondizio, J. Settele, S. Díaz, and H. T. Ngo (editors). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 1148 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>
6. International Energy Agency (n.d.). Central and South America. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/regions/central-south-america>
7. Ministério do Meio Ambiente (MMA) (2024). Contribuição Nacionalmente Determinada (NDC). Available at: <https://www.gov.br/mma/pt-br/assuntos/mudanca-do-clima/NDC>
8. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (n.d.). Land Cover (indicator). Available at: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=LAND_COVER
- 9 Plazas-Niño, FA. Et al. 2023. Informing sustainable energy policy in developing countries: An assessment of decarbonization pathways in Colombia using open energy system optimization modelling. Energy Strategy Reviews 50, 101226
- 10 Rochedo, P.R. R. et al., 2018. The threat of political bargaining to climate mitigation in Brazil. Nature Climate Change, v. 8, p. 695-698, 2018.p. 695-698, 2018. 0
11. Statista A (n.d.). Emissions in Brazil - Statistics & Facts. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/topics/10805/emissions-in-brazil/#topicOverview>

